

8T – The Coupling Constants Series and Curvature Hurricanes

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Abstract:

By analyzing the primordial coupling constants series under parameterizing the net curvature, and allowing partial energy release, the result would be a net curvature similar to an hurricane in geo-physics, which is fed by the partial energy release of original term. That is in agreement with the fact that the Bosons were proven to be curvature vortexes.

Introduction

The 8T setting is a Lorentz manifold, $s = (M, g)$, with (3,1) signature. The manifold is the connected manifold, invoked stationary, $s = s_0 \times \mathbb{R}$. The manifold has areas of extremum curvatures that remain as they are overtime, this are yielding time invariant acceleration from them on the metric tensor M, given by two conditions below (1). The reason for the acceleration in the 8T is that the manifold is a part of an infinite packet of universes, which interact at areas of extremum curvatures, as g is the Ricci flow, and as a result flatten each other metric tensor causing it to accelerate in a time invariant rate, given by equations (1.2) and (1.21). By (1.2) those manifolds are topologically invariant.

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \cap \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_1} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_n} = 0 \quad (1.1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_1} \frac{\partial s_1}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2)$$

Fermions are described by the arbitrary variation term on the main equation (1.3). By discretizing and partitioning the arbitrary variation term in (1.31), and by proving the series must have only two distinct elements that differ in sign and vanish to zero. By allowing the elements to vary, we proven they form threefold combinations.

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} \delta g' = 0 \quad (1.3)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \quad (1.31)$$

In the Riemann hypothesis we have proven primes to from non-abelian group. The condition under addition was to have odd amounts of distinct higher primes, to ensure a prime. Since bosonic fields are isomorphic to prime numbers, proven by the primorial coupling constants series, it is possible to predict that compositions of odd amount of bosons will yield a new Boson.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (1.4)$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30: 128: 850: 9254.. \quad (1.41)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \quad (1.42)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \quad (1.43)$$

$$8 + (1)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

For example the Electromagnetic coupling term:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.44)$$

Bosons a in the 8T are described by net curvature, given by the term (1.45):

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i > 0 \quad (1.45)$$

$$\delta g = N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0$$

Take as an example three unbounded net curvatures that are distinct. $N_{V1} = (+7)$, $N_{V2} = (+11)$, and $N_{V3} = (+13)$ each associated with a bosonic ripple of net curvature across the metric tensor according to the coupling series and the setting of varying manifolds.

$$N_{V1} + N_{V2} + N_{V3} = 7 + 11 + 13 \quad (1.46)$$

$$N_{V4} = +31; N_{V4} \in \mathbb{P} \quad (1.47)$$

Suppose that part of the elements, which are composing curvatures of the new term, N_{V4} , just vanished into energy. That is because even amount of variations in the 8T vanish, and two primes as was proven will always form an even number. The result of the vanishing of the terms is equivalent to energy insert that effect the remaining net curvature, which is prime and isomorphic to an element in the coupling series. that analysis ignore the spin representation as was presented in previous papers and below equation (1.43), as if two net curvature with spin one are combined, the result is a spin two entity. In this paper, the combinations of net variations is analyzed as pure energy which effect, or vanish into the remaining Boson "particle" net curvature with spinning vortex in the 8T, in our example the remaining particle is N_{V3} .

$$\begin{aligned} N_{V1} + N_{V2} &= \text{Even} \\ \text{Even} &= 0 \\ N_{V1} + N_{V2} &= \Delta E \\ \Delta E &\rightarrow N_{V3} \end{aligned} \quad (1.48)$$

The pure energy is the fuel, which is inserted to the prime which is left, N_{V3} . The process is similar to the geologic phenomena of 'Hurricane' in which hot air is releasing energy, and that energy than being used to fuel the hurricane, the colder air which went certain altitude above the original hot air altitude. That is of course an over simplistic description but the analogy is still holding. The analogy can be examined as the particles known as bosons are regarded to be in the 8T as spinning curvature vortexes. By adding ΔE onto N_{V3} , the result is that the vortex of the curvature increase, it is an extra fuel. Similar to the "fuel" the Hurricane is getting. Again, it is important to emphasize that in this paper we took the pure energy point of analysis and ignored the spin representation, presented in the articles about SUSY and Bosonic compositions. In this paper, and in particular the above example $N_{V1} + N_{V2}$ are considered to be pure energy and never got the form of a bosonic particle.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)